

IMPLEMENTATION OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODEL TO THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation.

The implementation of flipped classroom into classroom started Bergmann and Sams (2012) who made it popular. It started with a compensation of students who did not attend or missed chemistry classes. This point made new beginning for a lot of activities to be used in classrooms. Since half of time class time was spent on introducing new topic, flipped classroom made it possible for teachers to implement problem-solving learning, cooperative work and myriad of different activities which enables students to understand the topic better. To be more precise research works that focuses this paper will presents works on self-determination, reading and vocabulary. There are astonishing findings related these three topics in FCM (flipped classroom method).

Key words.

Flipped classroom, self-directed learning, vocabulary retention, traditional classes, experimental and control group.

Since I studied at governmental state university, I did not have a chance to experience international education system. In state universities most times classes are traditional where teacher introduces topic and students learn then take a homework. While doing my Master's Degree I had a chance to experience flipped classroom and it was fruitful because I was very much involved into class discussions and loved reading articles, then thought implementation of this classroom model would help learners in governmental universities, colleges, schools, thus some advantages are highlighted in this paper in order to understand how flipped classroom works and what it brings for both teachers and students.

It is clear that Flipped classrooms work best when content is the main focus, but for students who are above from pre-intermediate (in most 90% cases students are) for language learning and teaching it may work well too. However, while reading some research works, I was convinced that it may work even with students who are younger and in lower level.

Self-directed learning in Flipped classroom was investigated by Diningrat and Ngussa (2022) among 118 Indonesian students who are studying in 3 different public universities.

Research was carried out with qualitative method with oral interviews and interviews were recorded from students anonymously. The results of the study show that students were motivated to self-learn the subject matter and content, they learned the topic in their own pace which helped low performing students to perform better and come up with questions that they discussed in the classroom.

They stated that they became self-disciplined to engage themselves in the pre-materials because if they do not come prepared, they would not be able the topic that is being discussed in the classroom, because there is no direct instruction regarding the topic of the class.

All information is given through readings and videos. Students have to cultivate self-control of their time and resources. Moreover, this model helped students to score higher compare to students who learned content through traditional teaching.

Another study was conducted among 20 elementary level learners who are at 7th grade at school. This research work conducted by Yilmaz and Saracoglu (2022) in Turkey. The aim of study was to investigate how flipped classroom model effects students reading. Data were based on both qualitative and quantitative method. There was pre and post test to examine students reading pace, techniques and their performance in flipped classroom compared to traditional classes. Moreover, attitudes of learners towards FCM were observed through weekly reflections. The results show that when implemented techniques into flipped classroom students had more time work on it and did better in their post test compare to the results in their traditional classes. Since students could learn more, it is self-paced, they reported that flipped classroom positively effected to their reading and time management.

The third research work that emphasizes role of FCM in improving students' vocabulary retention is held in the city Van (Turkey). Researchers Sahin and Tavit (2023) conducted this research among 20, fourth grade pupils. There are two groups experimental group and control group. In the first group they are taught with FCM and in second with traditional way. Students took several pre, while, post tests and in pre stage they showed similar results but in other stages experimental group made a better progress. The shyest and passive learners started to participate more because they paused their video and learned the vocabulary in their own pace and thus it suited nearly all learning styled students. They were able to use vocabulary more accurately because they came prepared. This group was also able to learn more vocabulary even if it is not related to the topic. As a result, they cultivated autonomous learning skills. Learners also were stress free and confident which help them to have lower affective filter. However, there some challenges noted while interviewing pupils' parents. Two of students' parents said that low internet connection and bad technological infrastructure learners could not get prepared for classes and were more stressed because they kept silent while others were engaged. This will also lead to misunderstanding about the topic as well.

To conclude, it is obvious from the listed research works that flipped mode of classroom offers incredible opportunities for individuals' growth because input is provided for everyone in their own pace. Since in Uzbekistan's education system there is nearly no implementation of flipped classroom it would be better for

teachers who work for public schools, university, college teachers to suggest to their faculties this method and prepare together content with videos and readings and upload it to an online platform. Educators should make sure that students have access to internet and language being used is comprehensible. By that way students will be able to engage more in classes, become more inquisitive which develops critical thinking and teachers will be able to help those who are not coping with the material well. Secondly, it can be a good help for inexperienced teachers who are still not good at delivering topics, because they will be able to take you tube videos or their own videos with cutting down inappropriate statements or information. Finally, if not used in a large scale this article can be a push for instructors and professionals to implement FCM into their own classrooms. If they have enough resources to create video or to select suitable materials from internet, they should try this model in their classes. Tekkol and Demirel (2018) noted that flipped classrooms prepare students for life-long learning (cited in Sahin and Tavail, 2023). Students become autonomous and understand that they can contribute to their self-learning in a large scale. If implemented properly FCM can generate new education system where students learn more and develop themselves intellectually and like to challenge themselves to learn more.

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